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Research Article

Role of Teacher in Improving Students Writing Skills at Primary Level in AJ&K

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 13-Apr-23 Revised: 16-Jun-23 Accepted: 6-Jul-23 Published: 9-Jul-23	This study was conducted to examine the role of teachers in improving students writing skills at primary level in AJ&K. The current study was descriptive in nature and survey method was used for data collection. The population of the study contains 789 primary levels teachers in kotli AJ&K. The sample was selected by using a convenient sampling technique. A five-point likert scale questionnaire was used as a tool in this study. A statistical package for social science software (SPSS) was used for the analysis of data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation for the analysis of data. It is concluded that teachers motivate the students to improve their grammatical mistakes during teaching the writing skills. Teacher helps students to distinguish between small and capital letters. It is recommended that teacher suggest their students to use wooden writing board for improvement of writing.
Keywords:	Role of teacher, Communication Skills, Writing skills, Primary level
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INTRODUCTION

A teacher is an individual who facilitates the acquisition of knowledge, skills, or moral values by students. Anyone can assume the role of a teacher, and in some cultures, the teaching of school-aged children may occur in informal settings, such as the home, rather than in formal institutions such as schools or colleges. In many cases, paid and certified instructors provide formal education to students (Ndunguru, 2016). The specific duties and responsibilities of a teacher may differ depending on the culture, including teaching students reading, mathematics, art, religion, civics, vocational training, life skills, and crafts. Formal teaching tasks typically include designing lesson plans that adhere to established curricula, presenting lessons, and assessing student progress. However, a teacher's duties may extend beyond the classroom, including supervising extracurricular activities, accompanying students on field trips, and assisting with school event planning (Nasab, 2021).

In some educational institutions, teachers may be in charge of disciplining students (Cheng, 2010). Most people find that being able to write is essential. Because writing is an important tool for communication, education, and self-expression. People with weak writing abilities may find it difficult to succeed in school and find jobs (Graham, 2012). Many linguistic elements, including linguistic awareness, punctuation, spelling, and vocabulary, must be given in written form during the writing process. Moreover, writing calls for the stages of planning, drafting, forming, editing, revising, and evaluation. As a result, writing requires more work than other language abilities to convey meaning (Widosari, 2017). It is crucial to teach writing to children in primary school. Although writing is a hard skill, if it is taught through social interaction and considers the personalities of the pupils, it may be an appealing, entertaining, and even motivating activity. Writing is a kind of communication where a language is represented by written symbols. It is believed to be a very fruitful skill; different writers express their original views and ideas through written forms. Writing gives students many possibilities to look for contemporary ways to express their own ideas and thoughts in a foreign language (Gerde, 2012).

Instructors should act as role models for students to develop their writing abilities (Graham, 2012). Yet in order to improve their students' writing abilities, teachers must first realize that teaching handwriting, spelling, punctuation, grammar, and other comparable mechanics is not the main item that needs to be covered in the classroom (Ahmad, 2016). Instructors have two crucial roles in helping kids write: modelling their own commitment to teaching writing and supporting kids when they write independently. Teachers should take special care when modelling writing for their students to create a supportive and motivating environment, show how writing can affect students' daily lives, share particularly what they write as draughts with students, introduce effective writing strategies, teach various types of writing, and gradually transfer writing responsibility from teacher to student (Graham, 2012).

Being a role model for students in the writing process has been subject to change. For the purpose of developing their writing abilities, teachers can assign pupils the task of journaling their daily activities. By having students recap or culminate what has been covered in class, it can also be utilized as a review or revision tool (Shabbir, 2017). At the basic level, teachers are crucial in helping pupils improve their writing abilities. Instructors encourage students to become more conscious of the social nature of writing. Instructors provide their students the chance to discuss where they find inspiration. Consequently, the purpose of this study was to determine how teachers might help pupils write better at the primary school level (Peterson, 2010).

Research objectives

1. To find out the elements of writing skills involved in teaching the writing skills at primary level.
2. To identify the role of teachers in promoting the writing skill of students at primary level.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Education

Education is the thoughtful, upbeat, and respectful nurturing of knowledge and change that is carried out with the conviction that everyone should have the opportunity to participate in life (Astin, 2000). Without education, we are unable to know or learn anything, hence education is really vital to us. Education is the process of changing how people learn and how they use knowledge and ideas. Education is the process of encouraging learning, which encompasses the development of knowledge, skills, attitudes, beliefs, and habits. It is a means of acquiring all the abilities necessary for a person to impact their environment and reach their full potential (Mrunalini, 2010). Education has a positive impact on our attitudes and behavior, and it is a purposeful activity with specific objectives, such as the transmission of knowledge or the development of skills and character. These objectives may include the promotion of understanding, logic, compassion, and honesty. To distinguish education from indoctrination, many scholars emphasize the importance of critical thinking. Originally, education was intended to pass on cultural heritage to future generations. However, contemporary educational objectives increasingly include innovative concepts like learner liberation, modern societal skills, empathy, and advanced vocational abilities (Lindqvist & Nordström, 2021).

Primary School Teachers

The basic duties of a primary school teacher are to organize and conduct classes throughout the school day, as well as to assign and grade students' work. Outside of the classroom, they collaborate with other members of the school's staff and consult with parents as necessary, such as at parents' nights or when a particular student needs extra help. Also, primary school instructors are expected to set aside time during the school year to create lesson plans and learning tools, mark students' assignments, and attend parent-teacher conferences (Epstein, 2013). A primary school teacher aids student in the development of their reading, writing, and academic abilities. Elementary school teachers play a crucial role in helping children lay the foundation for their educational journeys by providing instruction to students in grades one through five and facilitating the transfer of knowledge (Gandara, 2005).

Responsibilities of a Teacher

Teachers are responsible for creating lectures, classes, and assignments that educate students on a specific subject or topic, with roles that can span from working with young infants to adult learners. They can be employed by a variety of organizations, such as research facilities, community centers, government agencies, and schools (Crosby, 2000). While the specific duties of a teacher may vary depending on the subject they teach, most entail general responsibilities such as assigning reading and homework, grading tests and assignments, and tracking the academic progress of their students. A teacher's main responsibility is to interact with their students effectively and deliver engaging, well-structured lessons that encourage learning (Nespor, 2000).

Communication Skill

In today's world, effective communication is essential both in professional settings and in our daily lives. It helps us to understand others and our surroundings, bridge differences, build mutual respect and trust, and create favorable conditions for exchanging ideas and resolving issues. The ability to communicate effectively is arguably the most important life skill, as it enables us to interact with others and comprehend their messages. The fundamental nature of the desire to communicate can be observed simply by watching a baby attempting to imitate their mother's sounds. There are four skills of communication such as:

Listening

Efficient workplace communication is dependent on an individual's ability to effectively process information during conversations. This ability is linked to their listening skills. Listening is the process of focusing on sounds or movements and attempting to interpret their meaning. It involves intricate cognitive, behavioral, and emotional processes. As long as people exchange messages, which call for effective speaking and listening abilities, communication is taking place. Without understanding the speaker, students are unable to communicate their ideas. Listeners listen, understand, and answer in a communication process. This study looked into the role of listening comprehension in the development of communicative competence and discovered that language input from listening to language materials helped learners achieve high levels of communicative competence. Developing linguistic abilities in the target language is known as language learning. Speaking, reading, writing, and listening are the four core competencies. Listening is ignored because we assume that learners will automatically have the ability to create linguistic competence in the language, not because we do not acknowledge the improvement of listening (Gilakjani & Ahmadi, 2011).

Speaking

Effective communication involves speaking abilities that enable individuals to express their thoughts and ideas in a manner that is clear and understandable to others. These abilities are essential for successful communication in both personal and professional contexts. In school, students learn to develop their speaking skills in English and other languages. Speaking clearly requires the use of oral skills, which can improve voice clarity and enable effective communication. Communication involves the transfer of messages between individuals, which enables them to connect, make decisions, and inspire change. Effective communication is critical for personal and professional growth, and public speaking is one of the most important yet feared forms of communication (Arnold & Boggs, 2019).

Reading

Reading is the process of interpreting written symbols, such as letters and punctuation, to derive meaning from them. The brain converts these symbols into meaningful words, phrases, and sentences. The skill of reading involves a person's capacity to understand and decode written language and texts. Being able to read and comprehend written communication, including emails, messages, letters, and other forms of written communication, is highly beneficial. Reading skills enable communication and understanding of written language (Bruffee, 2001).

Writing

Developing writing skills is an important aspect of literacy instruction, particularly in the early grades, as it forms the foundation for students to document knowledge throughout their education

(Datchuk, 2016). The Ontario Ministry of Education (2005) recommends five instructional techniques for effective writing instruction: modelled writing, shared writing, interactive writing, guided writing, and independent writing, which can be used from pre-primary school through to standard three. There are several approaches to improve writing proficiency, including the use of technology such as word processing and the internet, which has proven successful in developed countries (Ontario Ministry of Education, 2005). Burke (2010) outlines six practical steps for students to enhance their writing skills, such as writing recognizable letters, forming similar-looking characters, and printing recognizable phrases and sentences with proper punctuation. Teachers can use scaffolding, temporary social and contextual frameworks that support learning in a particular academic field, to build on students' strengths in writing (Vygotsky, 2015). Research has shown that learners have more opportunities to speak a second language in small groups, which can enhance writing outcomes (Storch, 2007). Additionally, peer work allows students to collaborate and jointly produce new language knowledge. Gagne and Parks (2013) found that employing small group scaffolding techniques helped students develop the language needed to complete a writing task, allowing them to rely less on the teacher and feel more confident about writing assignments.

E-journals offer students a safe platform for expressing their ideas and improving vocabulary and reading proficiency by receiving feedback from their teacher (Gagne & Parks, 2013). Peer review is also an effective method for improving English writing skills, as students are more aware of their peers' reactions and perceptions than those of their teachers (Bitchener, Cameron, & Young, 2005). For example, Fagan (2008) used self-reflection exercises in a diary format to assess students' understanding of reading strategies, providing them with an opportunity to consider how they learn and what they can do to help themselves, while also providing valuable information for future writing instruction.

Writing skills at primary level

Following are the writing skills used at primary level:

Reading Comprehension

Reading comprehension, or the capacity to read and comprehend literature, is one of the most fundamental writing skills. Kids must first be able to decode unfamiliar words in order to write, as well as instantly recognize a wide variety of words. The next step is for them to comprehend the meaning of word combinations, phrases, and paragraphs. A strong vocabulary is helpful in this. But reading is the primary method for learning new vocabulary words. Children find it difficult to even begin writing without these abilities. They'll probably have trouble spelling and writing texts that have any real meaning. Also, they'll struggle with editing and revision of their work. For those assignments, you must carefully read it again in order to find any errors or weak points (Ahmadi, Ismail, & Abdullah, 2013).

Transcription

Word production through bodily action is called transcription. This ability includes spelling, typing, and handwriting. Transcribing can be difficult for children in a variety of ways. Even after receiving instruction, some still have sloppy or unreadable handwriting. Some people handwrite quite slowly. Some may type adequately quickly and properly, or they may write legibly, but they have trouble spelling things on their own. Transcription can frequently be sped up by using a keyboard. But for some youngsters, the act of typing itself is difficult and interferes with their ability to write. Tech tools like dictation (speech-to-text) and word prediction can make

transcribing simpler for children who have trouble with typing or spelling. Another prominent tool used by pupils in school is spellcheck. help: teaching that incorporates multiple senses (Baker, Gersten, & Graham, 2003).

Sentence Construction

Children must understand how to create coherent sentences in order to write. But it's common for kids to struggle with comprehending and employing proper sentence construction. They might not know where to put the verbs or how the different verb tense's function. Sometimes they could create lengthy run-on sentences by combining numerous ideas. It might be difficult to correctly use punctuation, such as commas and apostrophes. Items like the distinction between an inquiry and a statement, as well as between a subject and a verb. Children must practice writing sentences using this knowledge a lot (Mccutchen, 2001).

Genre and Content Knowledge

Understanding multiple writing styles is referred to as genre knowledge. Children must be aware of the elements of narrative writing if they are given the task of writing a story. It must have a setting (who, where, when), as well as a plot (what and why). The persuasive essay is yet another illustration of a genre. Kids must utilize a position statement, arguments, evidence to back up arguments, and a summary of the main arguments in the conclusion while writing one. They might need to be taught the distinction between nonfiction and fiction, or between biography and memoir. . Many young people lack basic understanding of the world. In turn, their writing may suffer. Reading, field trips, and family activities can all aid in a child's background knowledge development. Before, during, and after, discuss with the youngsters what they are learning (Hyon, 2002).

Planning, Revising, and Editing

Writing has a procedure. To effectively convey oneself in writing, you must plan, modify, and edit your work. Prior to writing a first draught, skilled writers organize their thoughts or make quick notes on what they want to write. Strong executive functioning abilities, such as working memory and focus, are needed for that. they must choose how to arrange these concepts into paragraphs and a larger structure. This calls for retrieving relevant information from memory, such as genre and content expertise. Also, students should go over their writing again to edit for clarity and correct any problems. That necessitates knowing the rationale behind and the best way to modify the wording (Drucker, 2005).

Self-Regulation

In writing, the capacity for self-control is crucial. Self-regulation occurs when you decide how many words a document should have and then check the word count as you write. Self-regulation is when you recognize a sentence doesn't make sense at the conclusion and decide to change it. When children experience frustration, they may stop writing. But it's also self-regulation if they tell themselves they're getting better and can do it. Writing professionals do this instinctively. Children's capacity for self-control may be impacted by how they perceive themselves as writers. They value writing, right? Feel they are capable? What drives them to write? For some kids, self-regulation is challenging (Baumeister, Vohs, & Tice, 2007). On the bases of above review of related literature following research questions were constructed:

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was descriptive in nature and survey method used to collect the data. The population of the study was 789 primary level teachers in Kotli AJ&K. In this study, the sample constituted of 258 teachers of primary level in Kotli AJ&K. the teachers were selected using a simple random sampling technique from the population of the study. A five-point Likert Scale questionnaire was used in this research. The questionnaire was validated by two experts from the department of education, University of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir. Cronbach's alpha statistical technique was used to measure the instrument's reliability. The value of reliability was found 0.73 which was acceptable to conduct the final survey. The researcher personally visited the government girls' primary schools of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir and collected the data. Statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used for the analysis of data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage and simple mean for the analysis of data.

RESULTS

Table 1: Mean analysis of writing skills

Sr. No.	Statement	N	Mean
1.	I motivate the students to improve their grammatical mistakes during writing.	258	3.98
2.	I encourage students to master in English writing skill.	258	3.81
3.	I assign writing activities to students to improve their writing skill.	258	3.84
4.	I suggest my students to use wooden writing board.	258	3.43
5.	I want my students write English properly.	258	3.66
6.	I teach everything in simple way so that students can write easily.	258	3.63
7.	I regularly plan activities that involve students in writing skill.	258	3.43
8.	I focus on students writing skill.	258	3.58
9.	I help my students when they face difficulty during writing	258	3.62
10.	I conduct special classes to improve students writing skills.	258	3.49
11.	I always assign writing task to my students	258	3.67
12.	I feel confident in correcting students writing mistakes in English language.	258	3.55
13.	I help my students to improve their writing skill	258	3.59
14.	I always help my students to write new words.	258	3.63
15.	I help students when students write few words or sentences.	258	3.49
16.	I help my students write appropriate spelling, capitalization and punctuation in their writing	258	3.62

17.	I help students to write accurate sentence in English	258	3.55
18.	I help my students to write introduction for an English essay.	258	3.51
19.	I encourage students when they write their own ideas in English	258	3.62

Table 1 shows the mean score of writing skills. The table further represented that the mean score of I motivate the students to improve their grammatical mistakes during writing; N=258, M=3.98, I encourage students to master in English writing skill; N=258, M= 3.81; I assign writing activities to students to improve their writing skill.; N=258, M= 3.84; I suggest my students to use wooden writing board; N=258, M=3.43; I want my students write English properly; N=258, M= 3.66; I teach everything in simple way so that students can write easily.; N=258, M=3.63; I regularly plan activities that involve students in writing skill; N=258, M=3.43; I focus on students writing skill; N=258, M=3.58; I help my students when they face difficulty during writing; N=258, M=3.62; I conduct special classes to improve students writing skills.; N=258, M=3.49; I always assign writing task to my students; N=258, M=3.67, I feel confident in correcting students writing mistakes in English language; N=258, M=3.55; I help my students to improve their writing skill; N=258, M=3.59; I always help my students to write new words.; N=258, M=3.63; I help students when students write few words or sentences; N=258, M=3.49; I help my students write appropriate spelling, capitalization and punctuation in their writing N=258, M=3.62; I help students to write accurate sentence in English; N=258, M=3.55; I help my students to write introduction for an English essay; N=258, M=3.51; I encourage students when they write their own ideas in English; N=258, M=3.62. Furthermore, results directed that I motivate the students to improve their grammatical mistakes during writing has the highest mean score in mean analysis of writing skills.

Table 2: Mean analysis of Grammatical corrections

Sr. No.	Statements	N	Mean
1.	I help students to distinguish between small and capital letters.	258	3.59
2.	I regularly conduct dictation words	258	3.68
3.	I encourage students to improve their vocabulary	258	3.62
4.	I always appreciate my students when they learn something new.	258	3.66
5.	I help students to write syllables	258	3.48
6.	I always explore new things for the betterment of students writing.	258	3.59
7.	I motivate the students to improve their sentence structure.	258	3.52
8.	I observe my students can get new vocabulary through writing	258	3.66
9.	I help my students to improve their spelling mistakes.	258	3.40
10.	I help my students to make their notes during lesson	258	3.60
11.	I suggest my students to report write about the activities performed by other students in the class.	258	3.55
12.	I always ask the parents to help the students outside of school in their writing	258	3.50
13.	I allow the students to use spell and grammar check during writing in the class.	258	3.64

14.	I motivate the students to write new words in daily routine	258	3.57
15.	I assign class work and homework to students for writing.	258	3.48
16.	I observe my students can get new vocabulary through writing.	258	3.43
17.	I appreciate my students when they write quickly	258	3.50
18.	I motivate the students try to write their own words in English	258	3.50
19.	I encourage my students to write for pleasure in free time	258	3.51
20.	I always motivate students to check meaning of words before start writing	258	3.47
21.	I help students to use dictionary when they write anything	258	3.52

Table 2 shows the mean score of Grammatical corrections. The table further represented that the mean score of I help students to distinguish between small and capital letters; N=258, M=3.59, I regularly conduct dictation words; N=258, M= 3.68; I encourage students to improve their vocabulary; N=258, M= 3.62; I always appreciate my students when they learn something new; N=258, M=3.66; I help students to write syllables; N=258, M= 3.48; I always explore new things for the betterment of students writing; N=258, M=3.59; I motivate the students to improve their sentence structure; N=258, M=3.52; I observe my students can get new vocabulary through writing; N=258, M=3.66; I help my students to improve their spelling mistakes; N=258, M=3.40; I help my students to make their notes during lesson; N=258, M=3.60; I suggest my students to report write about the activities performed by other students in the class; N=258, M=3.55; I always ask the parents to help the students outside of school in their writing; N=258, M=3.50; I allow the students to use spell and grammar check during writing in the class.; N=258, M=3.64; I motivate the students to write new words in daily routine; N=258, M=3.57; I assign class work and homework to students for writing; N=258, M=3.48; I observe my students can get new vocabulary through writing; N=580, M=3.43; I appreciate my students when they write quickly; N=258, M=3.50; I motivate the students try to write their own words in English; N=258, M=3.50; I encourage my students to write for pleasure in free time; N=258, M=3.51; I always motivate students to check meaning of words before start writing; N=258, M=3.47; I help students to use dictionary when they write anything; N=258, M=3.52. Furthermore, results directed that Irregularly conduct dictation words has the highest mean score in mean analysis of Grammatical corrections.

DISCUSSION

The results of current study suggest that teachers play a crucial role in improving their students' writing skills. Teachers motivate students to learn and improve their grammatical mistakes and vocabulary, plan activities to involve students in writing, assign writing tasks, and help them to write new words and essays. Research shows that teacher feedback and correction can significantly improve students' writing skills. In a study conducted by [Zohrabi and Karimi \(2018\)](#), teacher feedback improved the writing quality of Iranian EFL learners. Another study by [Matsuda and Tardy \(2007\)](#) found that feedback from teachers and peers can enhance students' writing skills.

Moreover, using wooden writing boards and dictation words can also improve students' writing skills. According to a study by [Vygotsky \(1962\)](#), using writing boards can help students to form letters correctly, and dictation exercises can enhance their spelling and grammar skills. Assigning writing tasks as class work and homework can also have a positive impact on students' writing skills. According to a study by [Paulus \(1999\)](#), writing tasks can help students to develop their

writing skills, as they practice writing regularly. In addition to teachers' efforts, involving parents in their children's writing development can also improve students' writing skills. A study by [Graham et al. \(2012\)](#) found that parental involvement in writing activities had a positive effect on students' writing skills. Finally, allowing students to use spell and grammar check during writing can be a helpful tool for improving their writing skills. However, teachers should also encourage students to learn how to use these tools correctly and understand the reasoning behind any suggested changes. In conclusion, the findings suggest that teachers play a vital role in improving their students' writing skills. By providing feedback, assigning writing tasks, involving parents, and using various techniques like dictation and wooden writing boards, teachers can help students to develop their writing skills and excel in English writing.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Teachers motivate the students to improve their grammatical mistakes during writing and also encourage the students to master in English writing skill. Moreover, they regularly conduct dictation words.
2. Teachers encourage students to improve their vocabulary. Also, teachers appreciate their students when they learn something new. Moreover, teachers suggest their students to use wooden writing boards.
3. Teachers regularly plan activities that involve students in writing skill. Moreover, teachers conduct special classes to improve students writing skills teachers always assign writing task to their students.
4. Teachers feel confident in correcting students writing mistakes in English language. Moreover, teachers help their students to write new words.
5. Teachers always ask the parents to help the students outside of school in their writing. Teachers allow the students to use spell and grammar check during writing in the class.
6. Teachers assign class work and homework to students for writing. Teachers observe that their students can get new vocabulary through writing. Also, teachers help their students to write introduction for an English essay.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Students may be motivated to improve their grammatical mistakes in writing by the PSTs.
2. PSTs may appreciate students by giving them reward like chocolates, toffees etc. It is recommended that teacher suggest their students to use wooden writing board for improvement of writing.
3. PSTs may give creative assignment work/tasks/homework to the students. So, they did their work with interest. PSTs may help their students when they face difficulty during writing.
4. PSTs may provide opportunity to the students such as correcting their spelling mistakes and help them to write new sentences in a proper way.
5. PSTs may include extra period in time table for improving students writing skill.

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